

Dementia: A Brief on Screening, Diagnostics to Nanotechnology

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Introduction

- Dementia as defined by the CDC is not a specific disease but is a generic umbrella term applied to the impaired ability to remember (memory loss), thinking abilities, or make decisions that ultimately interferes with daily activities.
- Even though dementia is known to mostly affect the elderly, it is not a part of normal aging.
- Age and comorbid medical conditions are impactful factors intertwined with poor prognosis, hospitalization, and mortality in COVID-19 patients. Alzheimer's disease-related dementias (ADRD) are a vulnerable group because they often have underlying comorbidities. APOE-4, could possibly be linked to the severity of COVID-19.
- The different types of dementia from most common to least common are depicted in the figure 1.
- There are various screening and diagnostic tests available to screen and detect different types of dementia.

Figure 1: Highlighting Types of Dementia (image courtesy of Alzheimer's Association)

Diagnostics and Imaging Techniques

- The fight against dementia can be two pronged
 1. By early screening tests
 2. By quick diagnostic tests
- In table 1 we have highlighted key aspects that different screening and diagnostic tests
- Currently assessment for dementia usually includes the following: personal history, physical examination and laboratory tests (blood and urine) for vitamin deficiency, infections, metabolic disorders and any side effects from prescription drugs.
- Cognitive tests: Mini-Mental Status Examination (MMSE)
- Alzheimer's Disease Assessment Scale-Cognitive (ADAS-Cog)
- Mini-Cog©
- Neuropsychological Testing
- Brain imaging techniques such as computed tomography (CT or CAT) scan, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI); Positron Emission Tomography (PET) and Single-Photon Emission Computerized Tomography (SPECT)

Methodology of the Study

To better understand how to treat patients with dementia, we need to review the following points

1. Understanding the mechanisms and pathogenesis of dementia.
2. Currently available diagnostic and imaging techniques
3. The treatment options including drugs
4. Reviewing how nanotechnology can be an effective tool in drug delivery

For this we did a systematic and focused review of literature available on databases including PubMed, Google Scholar, CDC, and WHO, with keywords including 'dementia', 'Alzheimer's disease', 'Parkinson's disease', 'diagnostic and imaging', 'nanomedicine', 'dementia treatment', and 'screening tools.' Only Peer reviewed published articles having full text were included for further evaluation and analyses.

Risk Factors of Dementia

Figure below shows the potential risk factors that can lead to development of dementia

Figure 2: Risk factors of dementia

	Screening tests	Diagnostic tests
Purpose	To detect potential disease indicators	To establish presence/absence of disease
Target population	Large numbers of asymptomatic, but potentially at-risk individuals	Symptomatic individuals to establish diagnosis, or asymptomatic individuals with a positive screening test
Test method	Simple, acceptable to patients and staff	maybe invasive, expensive but justifiable as necessary to establish diagnosis
Positive result threshold	Generally chosen towards high sensitivity not to miss potential disease	Chosen towards high specificity (true negatives). More weight given to accuracy and precision than to patient acceptability
Positive result	Essentially indicates suspicion of disease (often used in combination with other risk factors) that warrants confirmation	Result provides a definite diagnosis
Cost	Cheap, benefits should justify the costs since large numbers of people will need to be screened to identify a small number of potential cases	Higher costs associated with diagnostic test maybe justified to establish diagnosis

Table 1 Key differences between screening and diagnostic tests.

Medications in Fight Against Dementia

FDA-approved medications to manage symptoms

- *Brexpiprazole*: Atypical antipsychotic.
- *Donepezil*: Cholinesterase inhibitor.
- *Galantamine*: Cholinesterase inhibitor.
- *Memantine*: NMDA antagonist.
- *Memantine and Donepezil* (manufactured combination). NMDA antagonist.
- *Rivastigmine*: Cholinesterase inhibitor.

FDA-approved medications to treat Alzheimer's Disease

- *Lecanemab*: Disease-modifying immunotherapy.

Pathophysiology of Dementia

In Figure 3 we can see a flowchart of the mechanism of neuronal damage and the progression of Alzheimer's disease.

Extracellular and intracellular amyloid β and tangles cause extreme toxicity, that results in synaptic damage and increased ROS that leads to microglial infiltration around plaque areas.

In figure 4, Traumatic Brain Injury causes alterations to blood brain barrier, in turn causing inflammation of the brain tissue and increase in α -synuclein, β -aggregates and NFTs causing neurodegeneration ultimately causing Parkinsonism like pathology.

Figure 3: Mechanism of neuronal damage and Alzheimer's disease progression. (Modified with permission)

Figure 4: Pathogenesis of Post-Traumatic Parkinsonism (PTP)

Role of Nanotechnology

- Nanotechnology is a very promising field in the development of drugs to get maximum benefit from drugs on the neuronal cells.
- The major issue in therapeutics is bioavailability of drugs and easy permeability across the blood brain barrier (BBB).
- BBB due to its selective transport of molecules reduces the efficacious delivery of therapeutic drugs, which results in the need for large doses of drugs to reach levels above the minimum effective concentration in the brain thereby increasing toxicity.
- Nanomedicine and nanocarrier systems provide an opportunity to overcome such problems for transporting active molecules across the BBB.
- Recent nanotechnology advancements recommend plans for more effective therapeutic and diagnostic options in targeted drug delivery with the aid of nanoparticles while increasing drug bioavailability across the BBB into the CNS with extremely minimal or no side effects.

Figure 5: Semipermeable blood-brain barrier and transmigration route of the nanoparticles (NPs) (used with permission)

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